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The Influence of Contemporary Visual Art on Everyday Life

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ABSTRACT

With the development of new media and the advent of consumer society, visual culture fills people's living space. Contemporary visual culture, with the powerful communication ability of contemporary media, has been involved in many fields such as economy, culture and everyday life. Visual art presents richer forms of expression in contemporary times, with the super-high communication capacity of new media. The impact of contemporary visual art on human everyday life is unprecedented. Rapid development has provided a new dimension for cultural innovation and also exerted a huge impact on human everyday life.

INTRODUCTION

With the development trend of Internet integrating various media, digital media integrates newspapers and magazines, film and television music, network communication and a series of new media forms together. As the most convenient communication platform at present, digital media has been seamlessly connected with our life. In everyday life, visual cultural products such as movies, TV, advertisements and electronic games are deeply embedded in People's everyday life. These cultural products not only bring us visual enjoyment, but also play an important role in spreading the concept of The Times and cultural connotation. With the continuous maturity of visual art creation under the new media platform, a variety of new technologies and new ideas have emerged. Through the display of digital media, visual art has produced many ways of experience that traditional visual art does not have. The expression form of new media has produced many positive influences on the innovation and development of traditional artistic thinking. Visual art has great penetration in everyday life through new media platforms, and the media also changes the communication and consumption of visual art and other dimensions.

LITERATURE

Cultural consumption has become one of the most important consumer products, and visual culture has occupied a dominant position in today's social culture. The greater comfort of the image makes the text gradually lose its original charm. Some people say that this is an "age of image reading", a term that vividly reflects the trend of today's cultural emphasis on images. The arrival of the era of image reading has the same essential characteristics as the "language turning", which is a transformation of cultural form and marks that human beings have entered the period of "image turning". In the second half of the 20th century, with the rise of postmodernism, the image theory better conforms to the development of The Times. In the field of culture, visual culture has become an important field of cultural circulation and concept communication. In the economic field, the visual design of goods has become the main concern of the production and consumption of goods. With the development of

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network technology and mass media, visual culture has an insurmountable position in other forms of culture. Visual consumption is the most important component of contemporary cultural industry. With the development of digital technology, the forms of visual cultural products are also increasing. "Eyeball economy" has a huge impact on the structure of the market. The publicity of product image design and aesthetic value has become an important link to maintain the operation of the market. In recent years, the importance of product image has even exceeded the trend of function. In such an environment, people's aesthetic concepts and behavior patterns have also undergone tremendous changes. The popularization of new media makes video cultural products have greater influence. The rapid development of information technology has changed people's cognition of the world. The emergence of new media such as computers and smart phones not only makes the types of visual cultural products more colorful, but also makes the consumption of visual culture more convenient. People can pay attention to their favorite visual cultural products with fragmented time at any time.

Innovation of Visual Art in the Context of New Media

In today's society, the booming development of digital information technology has influenced almost all media and art forms. The art forms of new media involve images, animations, games, digital photography, advertising design and other art forms, and provide a platform for the integration of various fields, so that the technologies and concepts of various art categories interweave together, creating more possibilities for artistic creation. The progress of science and technology has subverted the traditional idea of creation, and the new carrier also reflects people's aesthetic consciousness and cognitive way in the new era. There are various forms of expression of new media art, but all of them have the common characteristics of connectivity and interactivity. Instead of waiting for the result of creation, the audience can participate in and change the form of expression of the work, or even add new meanings to the work together with the author. New media art is the result of the combination of science and art. It can be said that it is the biggest trend of art development in today's society. The application and development of digital technology has given birth to a series of new art forms, such as video games and digital movies. The most prominent features of these emerging art forms are interactivity and virtual reality, which is a brand new art experience brought by digital technology. The speed and breadth of their communication are incomparable with the traditional carrier. The real-time interaction changes the viewer from passive acceptance to active participation. This approach has changed the structure of the cultural industry, broken through the limitations of traditional artistic creation, and provided various possibilities for the birth of new artistic creation ideas. This is the result of the inheritance, transformation and development of traditional art forms by new media.

In today's cultural consumption is beyond the scope of the scope of the so-called pure art into the everyday life, art activities also have already not be confined to art venues, but into the public's everyday life space, in addition to the People's Daily social activity space and living places, each in a new media access devices can complete cultural consumption activities. In these media, the boundary between cultural consumption, aesthetic activities and commercial activities has been blurred. The development of contemporary visual art must pay attention to the field of everyday life and broaden their creative methods timely. Contemporary science and technology is an important factor to promote the development of The Times. The integration of digital technology and visual art is one of the important features of contemporary visual culture. Science and technology broaden the horizon for the development of visual art, and visual art also provides a unique perspective for the study of science and technology. New media make contemporary visual art fully integrated with everyday life, and appreciation of visual art is no longer limited by art galleries, cinemas and other places, but can be obtained everywhere in the living environment. The life of visual art adds an aesthetic dimension to the consumption of products. New media accelerates the combination of visual art and consumption, and to a large extent promotes the formation of contemporary visual culture centered on visual symbols. In contemporary visual culture, the integration of art and life, while beautifying life, also makes art no longer monopolized by the social elite, but brings new dimensions to the development of art from the perspective of the public.

Although the cross-platform application of visual elements has changed the expression techniques of traditional art, the use of new media to perform a new interpretation of traditional art can also be said to be a re-creation of traditional art, or it is itself a new art. 3D special effects technology has brought the characteristics of The Times to the film from the perspective of new media, and digital technology has given a new meaning to the visual image of traditional Peking Opera. Digital media is an important platform for modern people to understand and explore social culture, and contemporary visual art has also reached an unprecedented degree of dependence on digital media (Yuidi, 2009). Digital technology expands the means of expression of visual art, and gives artistic creation a greater space for expression, so that movies and games can bring people more intense sensory enjoyment. New media art, as an art form to express the cultural and psychological structure of contemporary people, should strengthen the construction of spiritual civilization. , no matter how advanced technology requires the creation of the noble thoughts and artistic feelings as internal support, although digital technology can be a good addition to the performance ability of all kinds of visual art, but excessive addicted to the pursuit of sensory stimulation, will make the art creators losing the direction of the growth, the aesthetic orientation and spiritual lose value. Digital technology, like the paper and pen used in painting, is only the carrier of visual artistic expression. What makes works have artistic value is people's creative idea. Artists should transform digital technology into the era temperament of contemporary art, so as to show the unique cultural spirit and artistic value of contemporary artists.

The Interaction between New Media Visual Art and Everyday Life

The creation of contemporary visual art is closely related to the development of science and technology. In the digital media environment, the creative technique of visual art is always changing with the development of technology. Digital media facilitates the transmission of visual images, which makes cross-boundary cooperation in visual art mainstream. For example, after a visual image is created, it can be widely used in movies, TV, video games and other art forms. Plus the integration of cultural industries and the strong connectivity and interactivity of digital platforms. In the new environment, visual art enables people to have new perception and experience, and new media creates a brand new production system for visual culture.

In the Internet era, we are all living in an environment of multi-cultural integration, and the consumption mode of mass entertainment is also changing due to the rise of the Internet. The integration of technology, content and commerce creates a contemporary cultural industry that integrates cultural and commercial activities. The Internet has provided a more flexible and participatory medium, tightly connecting cultures and empowering the masses. Movies and games are two very popular art forms in the digital age. They use the same intellectual property rights in different markets. The integration of audiences in different markets can win more opportunities for the success of movies or games, and also enable a brand to gain a wider range of support. The works in these different media form a unified whole because of the same story plot and background information, so that consumers have no sense of inconsistency between different types of visual art. Famous movie theorists bela his thought: adaptation is "just as the original raw material, from the perspective of their own art form of this raw to look at the real life, and don't pay attention to the material with the form of" so (Balazs, 1979) game narrative structure can be generated by people's behavior of many possible, build the everyday life and art belong to different areas in the world, and it is precisely because has the difference to the integration of both to create more likely (Mingju,1994).

By integrating visual art into everyday life through new media, intellectual property can be extended to a greater extent. In terms of many experiences and methods in the transformation process of visual art, the narrative technique of games can be used for reference, and the visual, sound, script and other factors of games can be grasped, so that the living environment and visual art can be perfectly connected. Many games at development time to write a complete script to plan the process of the

game, the game storyline in the very great degree, presented through video and audio, in seeing and hearing level also built a space, with more and more mature, VR/AR technology game with the scene can be life together, and through the visual arts enrich the life world. When designers leave the game and try to create a new experience for the living world, the open nature of the game's narrative structure makes the living world a richer experience. Movies have more flexibility than games in terms of visual representation of time and space. People must be confined to the given play space and process. After the game selects the character to enter the virtual world, the fixed perspective will accompany the player all the game time. The film, on the other hand, can provide the organization of shots in accordance with the established method of creating a sense of continuity, and show a variety of visual entrances into the story space in the continuous lens language. The variation of lens types plays an important role in the movie viewing experience, and the creation of game products is also inspired by the lens language of movies. In the game products developed in recent years, many game processes adopt the narrative technique of the movie, and the perspective directly aims at the visual field of the game characters controlled by the player or the game characters controlled by the player can observe. The timing and spatial organization of the film and the game are very different as the story unfolds. One of the most significant differences is that in the context of the game, the storyline can be controlled by the player, while in the film, the director controls all the content displayed on the screen (Bin, 2008). The media characteristics of the game are established through the interaction between the player and the game program. The various behaviors and choices of the player will lead to different results of the game.

The Advantages of Cooperative Development of Visual Arts

In the era of new media, the integration of various media is getting higher and higher, and the visual images of products in mass culture are more and more widely used across boundaries. "Contemporary art is more mediatic than conceptual," says (Rush& Lurie, 2010). New media have changed the cultural connotation of contemporary visual art, and also the visual experience of the audience. New media technology makes the use of visual image not limited by a single form, the same visual image can be used alternately in different art forms. The cross-art transformation enhances the value of visual image, which makes visual art far more influential than other art forms in new media.

The consumption demand of contemporary society is no longer limited to the basic material needs. As people become rich, they have a higher level of demand for the experience of survival. The rapid development of digital technology make the technology more close to people's life, science and technology make people's way of thinking and emotional needs, great changes have taken place in people's demand for a brand new audio-visual experience has brought new business opportunities, digital media strong communication ability and its close relationship with the audience, means art in the form of digital products will have a very broad space for growth (Fuxing, 2003). The different taste patterns of the audience make each art form have different consumption patterns, and thus have different influences on the innovation ability, aesthetic value, audience's experience and psychological level of various art forms. In the digital media environment, the relationship between movies, TV, games and advertisements is getting closer and closer, and many excellent works are even completed through the cooperation of personnel from multiple industries.

Although all kinds of visual arts have a lot in common in terms of experience, and they can cooperate deeply in terms of creative elements, they should also pay attention to maintain their respective artistic characteristics in the cooperation. Only by accurately grasping its artistic value can the whole visual art industry develop healthily and well. As various art forms have their own personalities in some aspects, more coordination is needed in the transformation process. With the high development of science and technology, some artistic creations overindulge in production technology, but stay at a relatively superficial level in aesthetic orientation and spiritual demand, and even obscure the value and significance of the creator's artistic thought. Although digital technology has improved sensory experience, technology is ultimately a means of expressing artistic ideas (Danyuan,1999). Therefore,

artists need to improve their own cultural heritage and artistic spirit as a basis to transform technological advantages into artistic creation advantages. New media art, as an art form to express the contemporary cultural structure, should strengthen the inner shaping of modern society and humanistic spirit. No matter how high the technology develops, it needs the thought as the internal support, and the combination of technology and the requirement of art can make contemporary visual art have a living soul. In the process of transformation of visual elements, it is necessary to avoid simple piecing with elements or arbitrary tampering that cannot withstand scrutiny, fully understand the unique attributes of various artistic forms, and promote the continuous maturity of contemporary visual art in cooperation. While drawing on each other in art forms and cooperating with each other in the industrial chain, attention should be paid to maintaining their own independence, otherwise blunt adaptation or combination of neither fish nor fish will only lead to extinction.

In recent years, the artistic expression forms of film and television have become more and more abundant, and the combination of traditional artistic concepts and artistic concepts in the new era has created more fruitful results. The interaction and cooperation of various art forms have changed the expression technique, aesthetic value and even social significance of works. With the progress of The Times, digital technology has provided a broader space for artists' imagination and creativity, and the integration of visual arts has stimulated greater creative potential for artists. Creative ideas in different art fields provide the ideological basis for novel creativity, and advanced digital technology provides reliable material conditions for the realization of ingenious ideas. The cooperation between different art forms is an art form with great vitality and development potential. The adaptation of this creative technique is breaking the inherent boundaries and the limitations of the old ideas, training the experience cultivation and artistic pursuit of artists, and making the artistic style and aesthetic needs diversified.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There is still a long way to go for the development of all kinds of visual arts in the everyday life environment. Although there are many rough and rough places in the works at the present stage, we should see that various art forms have become a trend. New media provides a brand new platform for art to integrate into the world of life. Contemporary visual art is constantly expanding and changing in its connotation and expression, and its concept and form are becoming more and more open. Digital technology provides the convenience of virtual reality and social communication and promotes the development and innovation of visual art. The cross-boundary exploration of artistic pursuit by artists in different fields expresses the aesthetic experience and artistic pursuit of the digital age, which is not only the aesthetic paradigm of the digital age, but also the change of post-modern culture. Visual arts will bring people a more humanistic heritage of the masterpiece.

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